

THE MEDIATION EFFECT OF SATISFACTION ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TRAVEL MOTIVATIONS AND BEHAVIORAL INTENTIONS

SEYAHAT MOTİVASYONLARI DAVRANIŞSAL NİYETLER İLE MEMNUNİYET ARASINDAKİ İLİŞKİLER

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Abstract

Studies show that there is no consensus in the literature on the relationships between motivations, satisfaction, and behavioral intentions. Inconsistent results of prior studies are the main motive of the current research. The current research, it was examined the mediating effect of tourist satisfaction on the relationship between travel motivations and behavioral intentions. The population of the research is domestic tourists, and the research was conducted in Mardin which is found in Southeastern Anatolia, Türkiye. Research data was collected through a questionnaire and convenience sampling method (n= 390). The bootstrapping method was used to test the mediation effect. According to the results of the analysis, the hypothesis developed regarding the partial mediating role of tourist satisfaction in the impact of travel motivations on behavioral intentions was partially supported. Also, the mediating role has been found to be significant. The research findings were discussed within the scope of the literature, and some suggestions were made.

Keywords: Travel Motivation, Behavioral Intention, Tourist Satisfaction, Mardin

Özet

Araştırmalar, literatürde motivasyonlar, memnuniyet ve davranışsal niyetler arasındaki ilişkiler konusunda bir fikir birliği olmadığını göstermektedir. Önceki araştırmaların tutarsız sonuçları, mevcut araştırmanın ana nedenidir. Mevcut araştırma, seyahat motivasyonları ile davranışsal niyetler arasındaki ilişkide turist memnuniyetinin aracılık etkisini incelemektedir. Araştırmanın evreni yerli turistler olup, araştırma Mardin ilinde gerçekleştirilmiştir. Araştırma verisi anket ve kolayda örnekleme yöntemiyle (n= 390) toplanmıştır. Arabuluculuk etkisini test etmek için önyükleme yöntemi kullanılmıştır. Analiz sonuçlarına göre, seyahat motivasyonlarının davranışsal niyetler üzerindeki etkisinde turist memnuniyetinin kısmi aracı rolüne ilişkin geliştirilen hipotez kısmen desteklenmiştir. Ayrıca aracılık rolü anlamlı bulunmuştur. Araştırma bulguları literatür kapsamında tartışılmış ve bazı önerilerde bulunulmuştur.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Seyahat Motivasyonu, Davranışsal Niyet, Turist Memnuniyeti, Mardin

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1. Introduction

Tourism which is one of the most dynamic events in the world has a significant impact on the main economies of the world in terms of being an important source of income and employment. Therefore, many countries that want to have a significant share in tourism are increasing their investments in the tourism industry including various campaigns and strategies to highlight the attractiveness of their main destinations. In this context, competitive structure destinations in the tourism industry force them to struggle with various tourist behaviors and internal or external forces that significantly affect these behaviors. In this case, it is important to understand why tourists are traveling, how their holidays affect their expectations from the destination, and how travel motivations affect their satisfaction with the destination in order for destinations to gain a competitive advantage against these internal or external forces. The internal forces aforementioned can be explained as factors related to the tourists themselves, such as their behavior, motivation, expectations, and satisfaction. External forces may include factors such as prices, economic conditions, and marketing strategies that may affect the competitive structure of destinations and the tourism industry. It is important to understand and manage both internal and external forces for destinations to gain a competitive advantage in the tourism industry.

The concept of travel motivation in tourism research can be classified as two motives that show that individuals travel because of being pulled or pushed by some factors or forces. These forces refer to how people are forced to make travel decisions by motivational variables and how they are influenced or withdrawn by the characteristics of a particular destination. While push motivations are related to the tourists' longing pull motivations are related to the characteristics of the specific target/destination (Hasan et al., 2018). In this context, tourists are motivated to develop expectations about their travels before purchasing a particular product or service. If the purchased product matches or is higher than the tourists' expectations, the satisfaction level is also high, and the tourist is willing to buy the product again. However, if the tourists cannot meet their expectations from the product, the level of satisfaction is low, and then they can choose different products (Wong et al., 2013). As it is understood, tourists' motivations, satisfaction, and attitudes are related to each other.

Khuong & Ha (2014) found that motivations directly affect satisfaction and behavioral intentions. According to Yoon and Uysal (2005) push motivation directly affects behavioral intentions, but there is no such relationship between pull motivation and behavioral intentions. Battour et al. (2012) also found that motivations are directly related to satisfaction but indirectly related to behavioral intentions. Similarly, Bayih & Singh (2020) found that travel motivations were correlated with satisfaction, but not with behavioral intentions. The findings of Huang & Hsu (2009) and Suardana et al. (2014) also show that there are no significant relationships between motivations and behavioral intentions. Contrary to these studies, Khuong & Ha (2014) revealed that motivations have a positive direct relationship with behavioral intention (revisit intention). Lee (2009) states that motivations are important antecedents of tourist satisfaction and behavioral intentions. However, studies show that there is no consensus in the literature on the relationships between motivations, satisfaction, and behavioral intentions. This problem reveals the need for further investigation of the relationships between the aforementioned constructs. This need in the tourism literature is the main motive of the current research. Thus, it is aimed to contribute to the tourism literature.

2. Theoretical Background

It can be said that the tourists' travel motivation is one of the most important determinants of their behavioral intentions (Davras, 2020). Empirical research in the field of tourism also supports this idea. Davras (2020) determined that domestic tourists' travel motivations in Turkey positively affect behavioral intentions. Song et al. (2016), and Huang & Hsu (2009) concluded that the Chinese tourists' travel motivation positively increases their revisit intention. Alexandris et al. (2011) found positive relationships between visitors' motivations and behavioral intentions in their research in a ski resort in Greece. Khan et al. (2019) found that college students' travel motivation increased their intention to revisit. Kim & Park (2010) revealed that travel motivations positively affect the intention to revisit in their research on the representatives of private security companies. The motivation of relaxation has particular importance on behavioral intentions. Huang & Hsu (2009) found in their research that rest positively affects behavioral intentions. Again, one of the motivations that most affect human behavior is socialization. Culturally and physically refreshing needs are also important motivations that affect behavioral intentions (Kozak, 2002). Based on these findings, the following

hypothesis was developed to be tested in this study:

H1: Travel motivations significantly and positively affect behavioral intentions.

Tourists' motivation and satisfaction are the most studied topics in tourism literature (Devasa et al., 2010). Travel motivation can be an important determinant of satisfaction. What satisfies tourists is an important question (Prebensen, 2003). As a matter of fact, some researchers (Lee et al., 2004; Lin, 2005; Lee, 2009; Devasa et al., 2010; Harman, 2012; Tang, 2014; Kılıçlar & Aldoğan Şenol, 2019; Özkan & Koleoğlu, 2019) found that the tourists' travel motivation positively affects their satisfaction. Based on these findings, the following hypothesis has been developed to be tested in this study:

H2: Travel motivations significantly and positively affect tourist satisfaction.

Consumer satisfaction is an important determinant of loyalty (Akgündüz & Kızılcıoğlu, 2016). Loyal and satisfied consumers' behavioral intentions will also be positive (Lee, 2009). In research conducted by some researchers, it has determined that the tourists' satisfaction with the destination positively affects their behavioral intentions (Kozak & Rimmington, 2000; Yuksel, 2000; Duman & Öztürk, 2005; do Valle et al., 2006; Seçilmiş, 2012; Akgündüz & Kızılcıoğlu, 2016; Türkmen et al., 2018). The following hypothesis has been developed:

H3: Tourist satisfaction significantly and positively affects behavioral intentions.

Battour et al. (2012) found that tourist satisfaction has a full mediation in the relationship between travel motivations and behavioral intentions. In the study conducted by Khuong & Ha (2014), it is seen that satisfaction plays a mediating role in the relationship between travel motivation and revisit intention. Similarly, Bayih & Singh (2020) found that tourist satisfaction acts as a mediator in the relationship between travel motivations and behavioral intentions. Although the subject has been investigated in different examples in the literature, similar results have been obtained (see Lee, 2009; Suardana et al., 2014). Based on these explanations, the following hypotheses have been developed to test in this study:

H4: Tourist satisfaction has a mediating effect on the impact of travel motivations on behavioral intentions.

Figure 1: Theoretical Model

3. Research Method

The population of the research consists of domestic tourists who visit Mardin and stay at least one night in accommodation establishments in Mardin, Türkiye. Mardin is a destination in the Southeastern Anatolia Region where religious and cultural tourism is dominant. A questionnaire was used as a data collection tool in the research. The questionnaire consists of four sections. In the first section, there are five questions aiming to determine the participants' gender, marital status, monthly personal income, education level, and age. The second section includes the tourist satisfaction scale (adapted from Yoon et al., 2010). The third section includes the travel motivations scale (adapted from Kozak, 2002), and the fourth section consists of the behavioral intentions scale (adapted from Boo et al., 2009). The tourist satisfaction scale consists of three statements and a single dimension. The travel motivations scale consists of 14 statements and four dimensions (culture, pleasure-seeking/fantasy, relaxation, and physical), and the behavioral intentions scale consists of four statements and a single dimension. Likert scale was used to measure all three scales (1. strongly disagree, ..., 5. strongly agree).

No data were available on how many people the research population consisted of. For this reason, it was planned to reach at least 384 people based on the unlimited population (Cohran, 1962) in the current research. The research data were collected between 19-27 September 2019, on the day the tourists left the hotel. The convenience sampling method was used in data collection. At the end of the data collection process, 390 samples were reached. As the research data were collected in 2019, ethics committee approval was not required for this research.

Research data were analyzed using SPSS 23 statistical package. Percentage distributions were used to determine participants' demographic characteristics. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were considered to test the reliability of the scales and explanatory factor analysis was used to test the construct validity of the scales.

The SPSS-based PROCESS macro (Model 4) developed by Hayes (2012) was used to test the research model. Since the research model is not compatible with the models specified in PROCESS, a special dialog box was not used and a running command line was created on the syntax page. Each independent variable was evaluated separately in the model. Unless specifically changed, the required analyzes in PROCESS are made by default with a confidence interval of 95% and using 5000 bootstrap samples. These default values were used in the regression analyses performed with the PROCESS macro in the current research. PROCESS uses a bootstrapping method based on random sampling from data. In testing the mediation effect in the research model, the following conditions specified by Baron & Kenny (1986) were taken into account: The independent variable must have a significant effect on the mediating variable (path a). The mediating variable must have a significant effect on the dependent variable (path b). The independent variable must have a significant effect (total effect) on the dependent variable (path c) (Hayes, 2018). When all these conditions are met, for a full or partial mediation effect, when the mediating variable(s) are added to the model, the previously significant path between the independent and dependent variables must deteriorate or decrease in the level of significance, and/or decrease in the effect coefficient (path c') (Baron & Kenny, 1986).

The data were investigated from the point of erroneous or missing values, outlier values, and multicollinearity in data analysis. In the missing values analysis, randomly remaining few blank items were assigned values by Expectation-Maximization algorithm (Green & Salkind, 2008). As a result of outlier analysis, 20 questionnaires were determined as extreme values (tmax; 103.92529). These questionnaires were removed from the data set, and outlier analysis was applied to the remaining 370 questionnaires. It was determined that the t value (tmax: 48.10108) of the data was lower than the critical t value (Büyüköztürk, 2016) at the %1 significance level. In order to determine whether the data set is normally distributed, the multivariate normal distribution test was applied. It was observed that the correlation coefficient between mahalanobis distances and inverse

cumulative chi-square values found for the data set (0.797) was lower than the critical correlation coefficient (0.923) (Kalaycı, 2016). The fact that the multivariate normal distribution condition is met also indicates that the relationship between the variable pairs is linear. In addition, the fact that the correlations between the variables are not above 0.90 (Cokluk et al., 2010) indicates that there is no multicollinearity problem.

4. Results

57% of the research participants are women and 43% of the participants are men. 59.3% of the participants are married and 40.7% of the participants are single. 2.6% of the participants are primary school graduates. 1.1% of the participants are secondary school graduates. 12.2% of the participants are high school graduates, 8.5% are degree graduates, 37.8% are undergraduate, and 37.4% are postgraduate. 7% of the participants have an income below the minimum wage. 5.2% of the participants are between the minimum wage and 3000 TL; 8.5% are between 3001 TL and 4000 TL; 13% are between 4001 TL and 5000 TL; 13% are between 5001 TL and 6000 TL; 53% have a monthly personal income of 6001 TL or more. Finally, 0.7% of the participants are 18-24 years old; 31.5% of the participants are 25-34 years old, 25.6% of the participants are 35-44 years old, 23% of the participants are 45-54 years old, 11.9% of the participants are between the ages of 55-64, and% 7.4 of them are 65 and over.

Cronbach's Alpha general reliability coefficient is .829 for the travel motivation scale, .777 for the tourist satisfaction scale, and .772 for the behavioral intentions scale. In the social sciences literature, an alpha reliability coefficient greater than 70 is considered sufficient for the reliability of scales (Baum & Wally, 2003). On the other hand, items with correlation values below .250 should be removed from the scale, because it disrupts the collectibility of the scale (Kalaycı, 2016). Item-total correlation values were between .347-.637 for the travel motivation scale, and .364-.712 for the behavioral intentions scale. But between .135-.740 for the tourist satisfaction scale. In addition, when the item-total correlation value of .135 in the tourist satisfaction scale is removed from the scale (I am generally satisfied with my visit to Mardin), it is seen that the reliability of the scale will increase to .924. For this reason, this item was removed from the data set. As a result, all three scales were found to be highly reliable (Hair et al., 2010).

As a result of the factor analysis (Table 1), the KMO test being at least .50 and Bartlett's sphericity test being significant indicates that the data set is sufficient for factor analysis

(Kalaycı, 2016). As a result of the factor analysis applied to the travel motivation scale, four factors emerged as in Kozak's (2002) study (Table 1). However, it was noticed that some items were dimensioned to different factors. On the other hand, it was observed that the relaxation factor determined by Kozak and some items under the pleasure-seeking / fantasy factor dimensioned to the same factor in this study. For this reason, it was considered appropriate to name both factors as relaxation in this study. Again, instead of the pleasure-seeking/fantasy factor determined by Kozak, it was deemed appropriate to name the factor determined in this study as socializing.

Table 1:Factor Analysis

Travel Motivations (TM)	Factor loadings	Communalities
Relaxation (R)		
R1	,826	,710
R2	,822	,795
R3	,767	,686
R4	,748	,691
R5	,729	,645
R6	,682	,669
Culture (C)		
C1	,874	,803
C2	,868	,814
C3	,814	,711
Physical (P)		
P1	,903	,847
P2	,829	,757
P3	,699	,593
Socializing (S)		
S1	,753	,665
S2	,702	,666
Tourist Satisfaction (TS)		
TS1	,964	,929
TS2	,964	,929
Behavioral intentions (BI)		
BI1	,861	,741
BI2	,856	,732
BI3	,736	,541
BI4	,719	,517
TM: Total Variance: %71,811; KMO: ,766; Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: 1978,381 (Sig. ,000)		
TS: Total Variance: %92,901; KMO: ,500; Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: 356,456 (Sig. ,000)		
BI: Total Variance: %63,286; KMO: ,644; Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: 498,393 (Sig. ,000)		

Correlations between research variables are presented in Table 2. According to the table, there are low-level significant relationships between the tourists' travel motivation and their satisfaction and behavioral intentions. Besides these meaningful relationships, it is seen that there are no significant relationships between relaxation and physical motivations and behavioral intentions, and cultural, physical, and socializing motivations

and tourist satisfaction.

Table 2: Means, Standard Deviations and Correlations

	Mean	Standard Deviation	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Relaxation	3,3806	,89090	1					
2. Culture	4,6128	,66546	,280**	1				
3. Physical	2,5495	1,10251	,261**	,070	1			
4. Socializing	3,8563	,93955	,240**	,436**	,237**	1		
5. Tourist satisfaction	4,4368	1,17822	,190**	,026	-,009	,025	1	
6. Behavioral intentions	4,1264	,64113	,092	,277**	,024	,211**	,182**	1

** Significant at the 0.01 level

The results of the research hypotheses tests can be seen from Table 3. When the table is examined, the effects of relaxation ($P_c=0.0037<0.05$), culture ($P_c= 0.0000<0.05$) and socialization ($P_c= 0.0063<0.05$) on behavioral intentions are significant. However, physical motivation did not have a significant effect on behavioral intentions ($P_c= 0.4572>0.05$). Therefore, the H1 hypothesis was partially accepted. According to the table, while the effect of relaxation ($P_a=0.0017<0.05$) on tourist satisfaction is significant, culture ($P_a=0.6754>0.05$), physical motivation ($P_a=0.8814>0.05$) and socialization ($P_a=0.6822>0.05$) have no significant effect on tourist satisfaction. For this reason, the H2 hypothesis was also partially accepted. In addition, the impact of tourist satisfaction on behavioral intentions ($P_c=0.0334<0.05$) is significant. In this case, H3 hypothesis was accepted.

In the relationship between cultural motivation, behavioral intentions, and tourist satisfaction and socialization motivation, behavioral intentions, and tourist satisfaction, the conditions for path a were not met, although the conditions for paths b and c were met for the formation of the mediation effect. According to the findings of the relationship between physical motivation, behavioral intentions, and tourist satisfaction, the conditions for path b were met for the mediation effect, but the conditions for paths a and c were not met. The first three conditions for the mediating effect were met in the relationship between motivation of relaxation, behavioral intentions, and tourist satisfaction. Therefore, H4 hypothesis was partially accepted.

Table 3: Summary of Hypothesis Testing

	B	LLCI	ULCI	P
R→TS (a)	0,2511	0,0949	0,0473	0,0017
TS→BI (b)	0,0692	-0,0083	0,1301	0,0261
R→BI (c')	0,1013	0,0208	0,1819	0,0139
R→BI (c)	0,1187	0,0390	0,1983	0,0037

P→TS (a)	4,4617	-0,1383	0,1188	0,8814
TS→BI (b)	0,0835	0,0231	0,1440	0,0069
P→BI (c')	-0,0239	-0,0885	0,0407	0,4669
P→BI (c)	-0,0247	-0,0900	0,0406	0,4572
C→TS (a)	0,0453	-0,1675	0,2582	0,6754
TS→BI (b)	0,0791	0,0227	0,1354	0,0062
C→BI (c')	0,3228	0,2230	0,4326	0,0000
C→BI (c)	-0,3264	-0,2254	0,04274	0,0000
S→TS (a)	0,0314	-0,1194	0,1822	0,6822
TS→BI (b)	0,0817	0,0220	0,1414	0,0075
S→BI (c')	0,1033	0,0284	0,1781	0,0070
S→BI (c)	0,1058	0,0301	0,1815	0,0063
TS→BI (c)	0,2283	0,0182	0,4384	0,0334

R: Relaxation, C: Culture, P: Physical, S: Socializing, BI: Behavioral Intentions, TS: Tourist Satisfaction; a: Direct effect, b: Direct effect, c: Total effect, c': Direct effect

Another necessary condition for the mediation effect is a deterioration in the significance of the total effect and/or a decrease in the B coefficient. When the significance values and B coefficients of the paths c and c' are examined in Table 3, it is seen that there is a deterioration in significance and a decrease in the B coefficient ($P_c=0,0037 < 0,05$ ve $P_{c'}=0,0139 > 0,05$, $B_c=0,1187$ ve $B_{c'}=0,1013$). The absence of a complete deterioration in significance indicates a partial mediating effect. To verify this, it is necessary to look at the bootstrap values of the indirect paths in the PROCESS results. The analysis results of the indirect effect are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Accuracy of Mediation Effect

R →BI	Effect	BootSE	BootLLCI	BootULCI
Indirect effect	0,0174	0,0101	0,0009	0,0584
Total standardized indirect effect	0,0258	0,0147	0,013	0,0584

When Table 4 is examined, the bootstrap confidence intervals of the estimated paths (a-b-c) should not contain "0" in order to confirm the mediating effect (Hayes, 2018). It is seen that the bootstrap values (0.013 - 0.0584) showing the total indirect effect (paths a-b-c) have positive values, and there is no "0" between these values (Table 4). Thus, the partial mediation effect between the motivation of relaxation, behavioral intention, and satisfaction was confirmed.

5. Conclusion and Discussion

In the current study, the mediating role of satisfaction in the effect of travel motivations on behavioral intentions was investigated. According to the findings, tourist satisfaction has partial effect on the impact of the motivation of relaxation on behavioral intentions. This finding is also in line with the literature on understanding the effect of travel

motivations on behavioral intentions. First of all, the role of relaxation motivation in influencing behavioral intentions is frequently emphasized in the literature (Krippendorf, 1987; Hill et al., 1990; Kozak, 2002). Tourists travel to relieve stress, relax and spiritually heal. The motivation to relaxation can be an important driver in tourists' travel experiences and can determine their travel intentions. Research findings reveal that relaxation motivation can be effective through tourist satisfaction as well as its direct effect on behavioral intentions. The literature shows that satisfaction mediates the effect of push motivations on behavioral intentions (Lee and Hsu, 2013; Lee, 2009; Khuong and Ha, 2014; Suardana et al., 2014; Yoon and Uysal, 2005). However, the effect of socialization and physical motivation as push motivations on behavioral intentions was not found to be mediated by satisfaction in the current study. Therefore, these findings of the study partially support the literature. According to this research, satisfaction has a partial mediating role in the effect of travel motivation on behavioral intentions. This means that direct relationships, which may result from the strong attachment of domestic tourists to destinations, are stronger than indirect relationships. Since tourists are visiting their home country, their satisfaction level may not be the only determinant of their future behavior (Bayih ve Singh, 2020). Therefore, it is recommended to test the model proposed by this study by adding other mediating variables in the future.

It is also natural that destinations with significant cultural and historical attractions such as Mardin attract tourists with cultural motivation (Lawrence, 2008). In the studies conducted by Kılıçlar & Şenol (2019) and Özkan & Koleoğlu (2019) in destinations where cultural tourism is dominant, it has been revealed that the primary motivation of tourists is culture. The fact that culture is the motivation factor that most affects the satisfaction and behavioral intentions of individuals whose primary motivation is culture should be met as a normal result. However, a remarkable finding of this research concerns the mediating role of satisfaction in the effect of cultural motivation on behavioral intentions. As a matter of fact, in the current research, the mediating role of satisfaction in the effect of cultural motivation on behavioral intentions has not been determined. Khuong and Ha (2014), Battour et al. (2012) found a mediating role of satisfaction in the effect of pull factors on behavioral intentions. However, such a mediating role was not detected in the research conducted by Bayih and Singh (2020). Therefore, it is understood that there is no consensus in the literature in this direction. Therefore, it is premature to

compare the current research findings with the literature. The increase in research on the mediating role of satisfaction in the effect of culture as a pull motivation on behavioral intentions is considered important in terms of contribution to the literature. Research findings show that different dimensions of tourists' travel motivations may affect behavioral intentions in different ways. Cultural motivation includes tourists' purposes such as experiencing different cultures, observing the local lifestyle and visiting historical sites. Physical motivation is related to activities such as exploring natural beauties and doing nature sports. Socialization motivation includes the purposes of tourists such as meeting new people and being in different social environments. While these motivational dimensions may have a direct impact on behavioral intentions, they may not be affected through tourist satisfaction. There is a need for research that examines the effects of the dimensions of cultural motivation, physical motivation and socialization motivation in more detail. Future studies will help us better understand tourists' behavior and satisfaction towards different motivational dimensions. According to this research, tourist satisfaction positively affects behavioral intentions. This finding supports the literature (Baker & Crompton, 2000; Kozak & Rimmington, 2000; do Valle et al., 2006; Dolnicar & Le, 2008; Okello & Yerian, 2009; Osman & Sentosa, 2013; Tomar & Tomar, 2013). Therefore tourists' motivations, satisfactions, and behaviors may differ according to the culture (Hofstede et al., 2010). Therefore, it is recommended to examine the model tested in this study compared to different cultures.

These research findings offer important practice recommendations for hospitality and tourism professionals. Tourism destinations can increase the demand for their holiday travel by offering touristic products and services that target the relaxation motivation of tourists. At the stage of travel planning, activities and opportunities can be offered to meet the relaxation motivation of tourists. For example, offering options such as spa and wellness centers and nature walks can meet the motivation of tourists to relax and thus increase tourist satisfaction. On the other hand, it should be considered that the dimensions of cultural motivation, physical motivation and socialization motivation may have a direct effect on behavioral intentions. The effects of these motivational dimensions on tourist satisfaction may be more complex and depend on different variables. Therefore, there is a need for research that examines the effect of these motivational dimensions in more detail. Tourism professionals can target these motivational dimensions by offering

their destinations a variety of cultural, physical and social experiences. For example, various experiences such as cultural festivals, natural conservation areas, social events can attract the attention of tourists and increase their satisfaction.

As a final word, this research data was collected in 2019. Therefore, in the four years since the time of data collection, the whole world has had to deal with the Covid-19 pandemic. It is highly likely that the pandemic has affected people's motivations and behaviors. On the other hand, it is still possible that the economic difficulties experienced today will especially affect domestic tourists' tourism expenditures and tourism behaviors. For these reasons, it is recommended to repeat the model tested in this research with current data. In this way, it will be possible to make sound comments about the model tested in the research.

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Ethics Committee Permission

Since the research data was collected in 2019, ethics committee approval was not required.

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1. Author: %50

2. Author: %50

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